

SOEL: Supporting Ontology Engineering with Large Language Models

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Abstract

The influence of Large Language Models (LLMs) is currently boosting and reshaping current practices in numerous fields, for example computer science. Due to their high capabilities in natural language understanding, their impact has been particularly evident in the field of Natural Language Processing. However, other areas of Artificial Intelligence, like knowledge representation and ontology engineering, may also benefit significantly from these technologies. However, developing ontologies is still a challenging and time-consuming task even though many tools have been developed by the scientific community to assist developers, for example, for formalizing tests to assess requirements, creating human-readable documentation for ontologies, ontology assessment, etc. In general, a significant manual effort is still required from ontology developers for conceptualizing, reusing, and validating existing ontologies.

To alleviate such ontology engineering tasks, several works have arisen proposing the use of LLMs to support the generation of competency questions, the conceptualization of models from text, the identification of concept alignments, etc.). However, the tasks addressed in previous works are usually defined in a heterogeneous manner, with different scope, inputs, expected outputs and metrics.

In summary, there are no reference evaluation tasks (e.g., assessment is purely qualitative) reference datasets or benchmarks that help compare existing work against future efforts.

To address this situation, SOEL aims to explore the application and adaptation of (Large) Language Models in Ontology Engineering tasks by creating open reference datasets, defining evaluation tasks and comparison benchmarks through adapting state-of-the-art LLM models. Although SOEL's approach is independent of a specific domain, it is planned to assess the results in three specific domains in IoT (smart buildings), Linguistics (definition of terminologies), and Open Science (description of scientific artifacts and experiments).

Keywords

ontology engineering, language models, large language models, evaluation datasets, benchmark

1. Project information

- Project short name/acronym: SOEL
- Project full name: Supporting Ontology Engineering with Large Language Models
- Project website link: <https://w3id.org/soel>
- Start date: 01/09/2024
- End date: 31/12/2027
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- Project partners: Universidad Politécnica de Madrid

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2. Project summary

SOEL aims at supporting Knowledge Engineers or Ontology Developers by exploring the role of LLMs in the Ontology Engineering lifecycle. In particular, SOEL aims to address main development phases faced by KEs in 1) ontology preimplementation e.g., by determining whether a set of requirements is complete, or whether requirements can be derived from existing documentation 2) ontology development, e.g., to automatically derive an ontology model from a set of requirements, or whether existing domain ontologies may be reused; and 3) ontology validation, e.g., by helping understand assessment reports created by expert tools, or by proposing automated tests to validate an ontology. Although recent work has started proposing the application of LLMs in ontology engineering, this area is still mostly unexplored, lacking well-defined evaluation tasks, datasets, or benchmarks to compare current and future work.”

Starting from the hypothesis that LLMs are able to assist KEs in challenging tasks in the ontology lifecycle during the preimplementation, development, and validation phases, SOEL will leverage semantic web community knowledge in Ontology Engineering to generate new knowledge by advancing the state-of-the-art in the following areas:

1. Defining formal evaluation tasks and metrics for LLMs to assist KEs in ontology preimplementation, development, and ontology validation phases.
2. Developing reference datasets to assess all defined evaluation tasks, based on existing ontologies and vocabularies developed in the Semantic Web community.
3. Developing evaluation benchmarks and comparing results of state-of-the-art LLM models for identified tasks. When appropriate, we will adapt existing pre-trained models for each evaluation task.
4. Adapt existing ontology development methodologies, identifying when, why, and how LLMs may be used during the ontology development lifecycle.

Finally, SOEL will further validate the results obtained by applying them in the creation of ontologies for different disciplines like smart buildings, the Internet of Things (IoT), legal texts and open science.

3. Project available results

The project has not yet produced the expected results as the current tasks focus on the analysis of existing resources; however, everything will be available on the GitHub repositories and linked from the website.

4. Relevance to ESWC conference

The topic of the project, enhancing Ontology Engineering based on language models, perfectly matches the areas of interest of the ESWC. This topic was addressed in several publications at ESWC 2024, for example, regarding the evaluation of semantic models [1], the generation of competency questions [2], or tackling ontology engineering in a broader way [3] and [4]. As the project focuses on generating evaluation frameworks to compare approaches based on LLMs rather than proposing new approaches, works presented at ESWC during the last and current editions are candidates to be compile, aligned and reused by SOEL, contributing therefore to the long-lasting impact of ESWC publications.

5. Value brought by the project to ESWC participants

SOEL will provide a common point to gather, align, curate, and published in a harmonized way previous results from ESWC publications and this edition attendees. In future editions, ESWC participants as well as other semantic web practitioners will be able to reuse common evaluation tasks and benchmark to evaluate and compare their solutions toward LLM-based ontology engineering tasks.

6. Value gained by the project from ESWC participation

Being able to promote SOEL during ESWC will greatly benefit the project by establishing collaborations with researchers developing approaches to address different ontology development activities aided by LLMs as well as benchmarks or datasets for comparing approaches. In this line, the project also seeks complementary expertise as its goal is not to generate LLM-based systems, but to harmonize the datasets of the evaluation tasks and the benchmarks to allow fair comparisons between different approaches.

Acknowledgments

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